

Appendix A: overview of the conceptual framework

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Benefit category</i>	<i>Key performance indicator (KPI)</i>
Nature	<i>Nature</i>	-Individual organisms -Biophysical assemblages (ecological connectivity) -Biophysical processes -Biodiversity -"Nature itself"
	<i>Quantity and quality of GBI</i>	-Connectivity of paths and roads -Accessibility -Facilities -Location
Contributions	<i>Regulation contributions</i>	-Habitat creation and maintenance -Pollination and dispersal of seeds and other propagules -Regulation of air quality -Regulation of climate -Regulation of ocean acidification -Regulation of freshwater quantity, flow and timing -Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality -Formation, protection and decontamination of soils and sediments -Regulation of hazards and extreme events -Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans
	<i>Material contributions</i>	-Energy -Food and feed -Materials -Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources
	<i>Non-material contributions</i>	-Physical and psychological experiences, including learning and inspiration -Supporting identities
People	<i>Cultural aspects</i>	-Stewardship -Identity, sense of place -Heritage values
	<i>Health & wellbeing</i>	-Social relations -Physical and mental health -Education and knowledge -Safety and security
	<i>Governance & justice</i>	-Procedural Justice -Distributional Justice
	<i>Economic aspects</i>	-Jobs created -Profits for business -Value of properties -City attractiveness

Table A1 Overview of all dimensions, benefit categories and KPI

<i>Metadata</i>	<i>Scoring possibilities</i>
Level of implementation	Being measured and used Being measured but not used Potential indicator, easily implemented Potential indicator, difficult to implement Potential indicator, unsure if implementable
(Potential) spatial level	Household Project Neighbourhood Municipality Regional National Higher
(Potential) frequency	One time Twice (before realization of the project and afterwards) Less than yearly Yearly or more Monthly or more
Relevance	Very low – Low – Medium – High - Very high
Feasibility	Very low – Low – Medium – High - Very high
Clarity	Very low – Low – Medium – High - Very high
Credibility	Very low – Low – Medium – High - Very high

Table A2 Collected metadata for each indicator

Appendix B: Technical note on DEA and results for all four cities

Our data analysis showed that all cities seem to cover each of the three dimensions and choose indicators that are, on average, more feasible, reliable, clear, and credible. Nevertheless, we explore an easy, intuitive method to aid the cities in choosing a good set of indicators. Rather than purely relying on scientific literature to make this choice, we use the local authorities' input to fine-tune the indicator set to local circumstances. Ideally, a good indicator set consists of high quality indicators that require little effort and cover all dimensions/benefit categories. We propose a Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) (Cooper et al. 2004) approach to identify 'the best' indicators in the set. Since a simple DEA model does not allow for a prioritisation of the efficient indicators (all efficient indicators have an efficiency score of 1 in the standard BCC or CCR model), we apply a super-efficiency DEA model and Cook's algorithm to calculate infeasible super-efficient scores (Cook et al. 2009) in the software R, using the [TFDEA package](#). We describe the DEA model inputs and outputs below.

Inputs

Typical inputs in a DEA model are costs, labor, or time. Since exact implementation costs for the indicators were not available, feasibility and the level of implementation were used as proxies for the effort that is required for implementation. Since numerical data is required, both inputs were transformed into a numerical scale (table B1).

Outputs

In total, there were 12 outputs: credibility, clarity, relevance, and a coverage score for each of the 9 benefit categories (table B1).

<i>Input / output</i>	<i>Original scale</i>	<i>Transformation</i>
<i>Level of implementation</i>	<i>Being measured and used</i> <i>Being measured but not used</i> <i>easily implemented</i> <i>difficult to implement</i> <i>unsure if implementable</i>	1 1.25 1.5 1.75 2
<i>Feasibility</i>	<i>Very high</i> <i>High</i> <i>Medium</i> <i>Low</i> <i>Very low</i>	1 1.25 1.5 1.75 2
<i>Credibility, clarity, relevance</i>	<i>Very high</i> <i>High</i> <i>Medium</i> <i>Low</i> <i>Very low</i>	2 1.75 1.5 1.25 1
<i>Coverage of a benefit category</i>	<i>For each pair of indicator i and KPI j, there is a score x_{ij} that expresses whether the indicator can not (0), somewhat (1), or perfectly (2) measure the KPI. See table A1 for the complete overview of the dimension- benefit category - KPI - Indicator hierarchy</i>	<i>Each benefit category z consists of different set KPIs (S_z). The coverage of a benefit category by a certain indicator i is $\sum_{j \in S_z} x_{ij} / MAX_z$ Where MAX_z is equal to the maximum sum of all KPI scores in the set i.e. $MAX_z = 2 * (\text{the number of KPIs in } S_z)$. The score for a benefit category in the DEA model is $1 + \sum_{j \in S_z} x_{ij} / MAX_z$ since a score equal to zero should be avoided (Cooper 2004).</i>

Table B1: Overview of the inputs and outputs for the DEA model

Coimbra

Coimbra uses 9 indicators in practice and all of them are DEA efficient (table B2). An input-oriented super-efficiency DEA model revealed that there are 24 efficient indicators, among which all six indicators that are measured and used. Table B2 below shows all efficient indicators and their efficiency score. An indicator is *DEA efficient* when there is no other indicator that can achieve the same output with less inputs. One of the results of the DEA analysis is an efficiency score for each indicator; an indicator is efficient if the efficiency score is greater than or equal to one.

It is logical that indicators that are currently used rank high because they require the least implementation effort (see table B1; indicators that are measured and used get a score of 1 in the DEA model). If the city would like to expand their indicator set in the future, we suggest prioritising indicators with a high efficiency score. It is advised to look for efficient indicators that complement the current indicator set; DEA does not guarantee a balanced coverage of all benefit categories. Coimbra currently does not cover quantity and quality so indicator 4 or 55 would be a good addition. Since Coimbra also does not cover economics aspects, we would recommend to add indicator 110 (Number of airbnb within 300 meters).

Indicator	Efficiency score
96 Trees of public interest	1,38
4 Available GBI within (5 min) walking distance	1,34
69 Areas of National Ecological Reserve	1,33
110 Number of airbnb within 300 meters (that mention the park)	1,20
55 Area of green public spaces per capita	1,12
106 Number of volunteers (individuals, associations) that contribute to the management of the area	1,11
95 Areas under forest regime	1,10
130 City trees (cadaster)	1,07
66 Average cost for house acquisition or lease	1,04
38 Percentage of water losses in the water supply system	1,02
115 Number of visitors to the Science Center	1,02
29 Business density	1,00
30 Companies, according to CAE	1,00
31 Municipal business reception spaces	1,00
70 Area integrated in Natura 2000 network and in the National Network of Protected Areas	1,00
78 Number of species of flora and fauna of EU interest	1,00
90 Area of National Agricultural Reserve	1,00
97 Typologies of existing forests	1,00
103 Solid Urban Waste per capita	1,00

104	<i>kg of garbage collection in the valley per year</i>	1,00
108	<i>Shared photos on social media of the area (Flickr)</i>	1,00
129	<i>Cut trees</i>	1,00
131	<i>Number of planted trees (adults)</i>	1,00
133	<i>Number of planted trees (small trees)</i>	1,00

Table B2: Overview of the efficient indicators for Coimbra. Indicators in bold are currently implemented in the city.

Figure B1 and B2 below show all of the indicators in a 3D space. DEA efficient indicators are shown in black with the corresponding indicator number, all other indicators are in grey. Each axis shows the score for one of the dimensions, divided by the efficiency score (figure B1) or the implementation score (figure B2). Indicators that are located further away from the origin have high outputs (physical, contributions, or social score) and need low inputs (high feasibility or implementation, meaning low feasibility scores or low implementation scores, see table B1). Note that, although credibility, clarity and relevance are not shown in the graphs, these measures of indicator quality were taken into account in calculating the efficiency score.

Figure B1: Graphical representation of all indicators for Coimbra. Outputs are considered relative to the feasibility score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Figure B2: Graphical representation of all indicators for Coimbra. Outputs are considered relative to the implementation score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Genk

Although Genk measures 13 indicators, only 12 were DEA efficient (table B3). Genk covers all benefit categories to a certain extent, but governance and justice is covered the least. Therefore, indicator 96 'diversity composition "Friends of the Stiemerbeek"', would be an interesting indicator to complement the current indicator set. "Friends of the Stiemerbeek" is a group of volunteer that have a soft spot for the valley of the Stiemer (a river).

Indicator	Efficiency
24 Survey "satisfaction of green in your neighborhood" (indicator municipality)	1,68
12 Number of watercourses restored in the valley	1,38
96 Diversity composition "Friends of the Stiemerbeek"	1,38
43 Number of overnight stays tourists / day tourists	1,21
77 Water quality: stream & pond	1,17
85 Qualitative meeting/questioning with the "friends of the Stiemerbeek" yearly related to the policy goals	1,13
93 Number of citizen present at participation moments	1,12
59 Number of "Stiemerdeals" in the area (total or per year)	1,09
60 Number of m ² (shared) vegetable gardens	1,09
76 Number of species of fish	1,09
3 Number of exceeds of measured (ground) water levels	1,08
64 Number of (cafe)-terrasses bordering the valley	1,06
29 Number of events organized in public space per year	1,05
1 Number of m ³ overflow/year (discharge of excess rainwater and untreated wastewater from the sewerage system)	1,03
30 Number of applications for events per year	1,02
5 Water quality/year of the Stiemerbeek	1,00
21 Hits on websites, social media indicators related to the valley	1,00
22 OSM-infrastructure - Open Street Map number of new registered users in the area	1,00
26 Survey number of visits per year	1,00
32 Number of km of hiking trail in the valley	1,00
33 Number of km of cycling paths in the valley	1,00
74 Number of macrophytes	1,00
75 Number of macro-invertebrates	1,00
79 Number of use of shared bikes	1,00

Table B3: Overview of the efficient indicators for Genk. Indicators in bold are currently implemented in the city.

Figure B3: Graphical representation of all indicators for Genk. Outputs are considered relative to the feasibility score. Indicators in black are efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Figure B4: Graphical representation of all indicators for Genk. Outputs are considered relative to the implementation score. Indicators in black are efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Leipzig

The Leipzig municipality currently measures and uses six indicators to assess urban green infrastructure. If the city would like to expand their indicator set in the future, we suggest prioritising indicators 16, 26, 1, and 12. It is advised to look for efficient indicators that complement the current indicator set; DEA does not guarantee a balanced coverage of all benefit categories. Accounting for the coverage of benefit categories, 16 and 26 are the most interesting as they cover the ‘material contributions’ category which is lacking in Leipzig.

	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Efficiency score</i>
25	Tree sponsorships	1,50
16	<i>Edible plants at mundraub.org</i>	1,38
8	Area of green space / capita (district wide)	1,24
17	Tree cover	1,14
26	<i>Urban gardening activities</i>	1,10
18	Noise	1,08
1	<i>Number of tree species (Richness)</i>	1,07
12	<i>Number of sport facilities (football, basketball, running tracks, etc.)</i>	1,07
24	Facilities: playgrounds	1,06
6	Share of sealed area	1,00

Table B4: Overview of the 10 most efficient indicators for Leipzig. Indicators in bold are currently implemented in the city.

Figure B5 and B6 below show all of the indicators in a 3D space. Each axis shows the score for one of the dimensions, divided by the efficiency score (figure B5) or the implementation score (figure B6). Indicators that are located further away from the origin have high outputs (physical, contributions, or social score) and need low inputs (High feasibility or implementation, meaning low feasibility scores or low implementation scores, see table B1).

Figure B5: Graphical representation of all indicators for Leipzig. Outputs are considered relative to the feasibility score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Figure B6: Graphical representation of all indicators for Leipzig. Outputs are considered relative to the implementation score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Vilnius

Vilnius measures and uses 10 indicators, all of them are efficient (table B5). Vilnius currently covers all benefit categories but 'Health and wellbeing' and 'Nonmaterial contributions' are covered the least. Therefore, we would recommend indicator 53 (covering health and wellbeing) and indicator 40 (covering nonmaterial contributions).

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Efficiency score</i>
53 <i>No of public information and dissemination activities about new management practices</i>	1,80
39 <i>Wood harvested (in volume)</i>	1,38
34 <i>Number of business/ services (e.g. kiosk, restaurant)</i>	1,33
17 <i>Walking/cycling paths between GBI</i>	1,30
4 <i>Land-use/land cover</i>	1,28
36 <i>Number of volunteers in the park</i>	1,26
6 <i>Ratio of impervious and impermeable Boils (land cover)</i>	1,25
21 <i>Number of natural heritage areas</i>	1,25
40 <i>Urban gardening activities</i>	1,24
16 <i>Bus stations near the park</i>	1,10
7 <i>Forest type (can be expert based)</i>	1,10
3 <i>Number of red list species</i>	1,08
26 <i>Number of sport facilities (football, basketball, running tracks, etc.)</i>	1,04
14 <i>Costs made for combating unwanted species</i>	1,03
1 <i>Conservation area</i>	1,02
25 <i>Number of green facilities (lawns, picnic areas, dog meadows)</i>	1,02
15 <i>Distance to roads</i>	1,00
20 <i>Number of cultural heritage sites, monuments</i>	1,00
23 <i>Area of green space/ capita (district wide)</i>	1,00
24 <i>Area of green space/ capita within 300m (5 min walking distance)</i>	1,00
32 <i>% of budget spent on recreation infrastructure</i>	1,00
33 <i>% budget spent on parks' nature maintenance</i>	1,00
35 <i>People employed inside the park</i>	1,00

Table B5: Overview of the efficient indicators for Vilnius. Indicators in bold are currently implemented in the city.

Figure B7: Graphical representation of all indicators for Vilnius. Outputs are considered relative to the feasibility score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

Figure B8: Graphical representation of all indicators for Vilnius. Outputs are considered relative to the implementation score. Indicators in black are DEA efficient (efficiency score ≥ 1).

References

Cook, W.D., Liang, L., Zha, Y. and Zhu, J., 2009. A modified super-efficiency DEA model for infeasibility. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 60(2), pp.276-281.

Cooper, W.W., Seiford, L.M. and Zhu, J., 2004. Data envelopment analysis. In *Handbook on data envelopment analysis* (pp. 1-39). Springer, Boston, MA.